

DAMAGE GROWTH IN NOTCHED CFRP LAMINATES UNDER CONSTANT AND VARIABLE AMPLITUDE LOADING

Vittorio Giavotto

(Aerospace Eng. Dept., Politecnico di Milano, Italy)

Giuseppe Sala

(Foresio Foundation, Milano, Italy)

Luigi Lazzeri

(Aerospace Eng. Dept., Università di Pisa, Italy)

Gao Zhentong, Zhang Gong-xing, Yang Nai-bin

(Flight Vehicle Design and Appl. Mech. Dept., Beijing Inst. of Aer. and Astr., People's Republic of China).

ABSTRACT

The paper describes some preliminary results of an experimental activity, still in progress, performed within the frame of a scientific co-operation between China and Italy about fatigue damage growth in composites. Tests have been carried out both under constant and variable amplitude loading using CFRP notched specimens.

The first part of this preliminary study was common for all the Laboratories involved in the activity, in order to assess the homogeneity of testing and measurement methodologies, while in the second part of the research program the influence of stress ratio on damage growth as well as on stiffness reduction has been investigated separately, for each Laboratory.

The effect of variable amplitude loading and of some changement in the load spectrum has also been assessed.

Further, stiffness variations have been correlated with damage growth, evaluated by means of NDE techniques such as dye-penetrant-enhanced X-rays and ultrasonic C-scan.

INTRODUCTION

Experimental activity about fatigue and damage mechanics in composite materials must necessarily be grounded on a large statistical basis, due to the high number of parameters involved and to their intrinsic high scatter. Fatigue testing is usually much time-consuming and therefore, in order to obtain significant and reliable results in reasonably short times, it is quite appropriate that Research Institutes and Laboratories work in co-operation on a unique research program. This joint effort provides notable synergies only if common experimental methodologies are defined and set up. Besides, as a fall out of this approach, a uniform standard of test methodology is reached in all the Laboratories involved, highlighting many causes of systematic errors. The joint research program which will be briefly described in the following is inserted within the frame of the co-operation between China and Italy about fatigue damage growth in composites.

RESEARCH PROGRAM

The collaborative research program between Italy and People's Republic of China is aimed at pursuing three fundamental objectives:

- (a) to identify and clearly define test procedures, measurement methods and NDI techniques with adequate accuracy to obtain reliable results;
- (b) to uniform such methodologies through the engagement of different Laboratories of the two countries on the same testing activity, so to identify, by means of the comparison of the results, possible critical causes responsible of differences;
- (c) to study and obtain original and consistent results about the onset and propagation of damage in CFRP specimens under constant amplitude (CA) and spectrum loading.

Agusta Helicopters co-operated in the program, supplying 204 specimens, subsequently divided in 17 batches, each one of 12 specimens, tested in the following loading conditions: static tensile test, CA fatigue tests with different values of the stress ratio (0.1, -0.5, -1, -2, 10), variable amplitude (VA) tests under a basic and modified load spectrum described in the following.

Static tests, CA ($R=-1$) and VA fatigue tests under basic spectrum were performed in all the three Laboratories to evaluate the results consistency. All the results have been summarized in curves showing stiffness decay versus number of cycles, Woehler S-N curves for various stiffness losses and ultrasonic C-scan and X-ray pictures.

TEST METHODOLOGY

The material used in this research was Toray T300 carbon fibers in epoxy resin Ciba 5208 pre-pregs, each lamina having a nominal thickness of 0.18 mm. The elastic characteristics of each layer are:

$$E_1 = 181.00 \text{ GPa} \quad E_t = 10.30 \text{ GPa} \quad G = 7.17 \text{ GPa} \quad \nu_{lt} = 0.28$$

The coupons were cut from quasi-isotropic laminate ($90^\circ/0^\circ/+45^\circ/-45^\circ$), 1.44 mm in thickness, with the following experimentally measured characteristics:

$$E_1 = 43.00 \text{ GPa} \quad \sigma_f = 398.0 \text{ MPa}$$

The specimen geometry is shown in Fig. 1; the notch consists of a hole, 5 mm in diameter, drilled in the center of the coupon.

All the tests have been performed at room temperature dry, at the frequency of 10 Hz, using electrohydraulic servo controlled fatigue machines. A strain gauge extensometer, class 0.1, gauge length 25 mm, was used for elongation measurements. NDE techniques were transmission ultrasonic C-scan and dye-penetrant-enhanced X-rays. Due to the shape of the specimens, particularly prone to buckling, anti-buckling guides (ABG) have been used, both for tension-compression (T-C) and tension-tension (T-T) loading, in order to assure uniform experimental conditions. Each batch of 12 specimens was subdivided into three groups of 4 specimens each, tested at the same stress level.

The typical test was carried out in the following way: a preliminary NDE control was made in order to assess the presence of possible defects due to manufacturing, then the reference secant stiffness of the virgin specimen was measured through a static test; finally the fatigue test started. At regular intervals, fatigue cycling was stopped, the stress-strain diagram evaluated and the secant stiffness measured again; besides NDE controls were carried out for correlating stiffness change with damage growth.

With the only exception of NDE controls, all the test procedure was driven by a computer-supervised control system², programmed to stop the test when a fixed number

of cycles or stiffness reduction is obtained, and to take more frequent stiffness measurements in the final stage of fatigue life, when the reduction rate becomes higher.

RESULTS

In the following the results relevant only to the first part of the test program will be briefly described, being the whole research still in progress.

The comparison of experimental results and NDI controls has highlighted significant features in the test methodology, particularly as far as ABG and extensometer use is concerned. The specimen geometry was derived on the basis of experience gained in fatigue testing of metallic materials, essentially dominated by tensile loading; on the contrary, compressive fatigue loads are particularly damaging for composite materials^{3,4}. In the present investigation compressive loading has been extensively used, so that the use of ABG was mandatory in order to avoid overall buckling. Such devices deeply influence the onset and propagation of fatigue damage⁵, as shown in Figs.2 and 3, which are relevant to specimens tested in the same loading conditions with and without ABG. In the same way also the mounting of the extensometer induces a notable modification in damage pattern, owing to the pressure applied by the knife which inhibits a regular delamination growth (Fig.4). Besides, even the ABG mounting procedures may become critical; if too much tightened, the stress-strain curve shows an hysteresis loop, due to friction forces generated between the inner teflon layer of ABG and the specimen itself: this phenomenon can alter the apparent value of secant stiffness, as shown in Fig.5.

The results relevant to CA T-T tests (R=0.1) are reported in Fig.6, which shows that for σ_{\max}/σ_f equal to 0.5 and 0.6 the stiffness loss is within 10% up to 2 millions cycles, while for higher stress levels a dramatic decay is observed from 300,000 cycles on; X-rays and C-scan NDE controls, reported in Figs.2 and 7, show the damage developed around the notch, responsible for stiffness decrease.

Also CA T-C tests (R=-1) have pointed out a similar trend, Fig.8; for σ_{\max}/σ_f equal to 0.3 and 0.35, stiffness loss is limited to 10-15% up to 2 millions cycles, while for the higher stress level the decay reaches 25% already at 300,000 cycles. Figs.9 and 10 show the relevant damage state, different from the one previously observed^{6,7}.

For composite materials, it is not meaningful to use Woehler curves related to failure, because progressive damage growth implies notable stiffness decrease well before final failure. For example, in aircraft structures, due to aeroelastic reasons, a stiffness decay of 5-10% is already unacceptable. Fig.11 shows Woehler curves related to 2 and 5% stiffness loss for CA T-T and T-C fatigue tests.

VA tests have been performed under a load sequence composed by 12,600 cycles (basic spectrum), whose cumulative frequency diagram is reported in Fig.12. This spectrum was derived from an on-board strain gauge recording of a helicopter fuselage panel, condensed to reduce testing times⁸. The basic sequence was then modified superimposing a tensile load equal to 10% of failure load (shifted spectrum); other modifications (e.g. truncation of tensile or compressive high peaks) will also be performed in order to evaluate their influence on the damage development process⁹. Fig.13 shows stiffness decay vs. cycles for the basic spectrum with σ_{\min}/σ_f equal to 0.40, 0.45 and 0.50. On the other hand, Fig.14 reports similar plots for the tensile shifted spectrum for σ_{\min}/σ_f equal to 0.30, 0.35 and 0.40. Corresponding damage state are shown in Figs. 15 and 16. Finally Fig.17 reports Woehler curves referred to 2 and 5% stiffness loss both for basic and shifted spectrum.

CONCLUSIONS

As far as methodology is concerned, the present research activity has pointed out some important topics:

- a) ABG strongly influence damage onset and development process;
- b) special care must be used in mounting extensometers because they can significantly alter the delamination growth;
- c) in future fatigue testing of composite materials, it is recommended to develop specimens able to sustain compressive loads without ABG.

The experimental results so far obtained confirm the high sensitivity of composite materials to compressive loads, and also the existence of a sort of "fatigue limit", below which damage does not dramatically propagate.

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Fig.1 - Specimen and ABG geometry.

Fig.2 - Damage development in a coupon with ABG (T-T).

Fig.3 - Damage development in a coupon without ABG (T-T).

Fig.4 - Damage development in a coupon without extensometer (T-T).

Fig.5 - Influence of ABG clamping pressure on stress-strain diagram.

Fig. 6 - Stiffness decrease of CA T-T specimens.

Fig. 7 - C-scan of a CA T-T fatigue tested coupons.

Fig. 8 - Stiffness decrease of CA T-C specimens.

Fig. 9 - X-rays image of a CA T-C fatigue tested coupons.

Fig. 10 - C-scan image of a CA T-C fatigue tested coupon.

Fig. 11 - Woehler curves of CA fatigue tests.

Fig. 12 - Cumulative frequency diagram for basic spectrum.

Fig. 13 - Stiffness decrease (basic spectrum).

Fig. 14 - Stiffness decrease (shifted spectrum).

Fig. 15 - X-rays image of a VA fatigue tested coupon (basic spectrum).

Fig. 16 - X-rays image of a VA fatigue tested coupon (shifted spectrum).

Fig. 17 - Woehler curves of VA fatigue tests.